

THE ACTIVITY OF THE NEIGHBORHOOD LAW ENFORCEMENT OFFICE IN THE PREVENTION OF CRIMES

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ABSTRACT

As a result of the attention paid to the field of crime prevention, the crime rate has been significantly reduced so far, and we believe that these indicators will become more positive in the coming years. For this reason, attention to the field should not be reduced even for a moment. Peace is a great blessing. Peacekeepers know very well how important and sweet this blessing is. The population also realizes how important and necessary this blessing is, which is why society and the state are developing and growing.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, complex measures are being implemented in the Republic to prevent crimes and combat crime, and positive results have been achieved in ensuring law and order in the country and significantly improving the criminogenic situation. At the same time, the work forms and methods of the state bodies implementing crime prevention do not fully meet today's requirements, primarily due to insufficient use of information and communication technologies.

Nowadays, even though neighborhood law enforcement centers have started their activities in many areas, this process has not yet started, and this process is reflected in the fact that this process is limited to the base points that were created before the neighborhood law enforcement center. First of all, this indicates a small number of preventive inspectors, the solution to this is to increase the headquarters and increase the number of inspectors in turn, because in remote areas, 5, 6 base points form one neighborhood law enforcement center, but the cooperation of these base points is not very significant. First, to reform the entire system, it will be necessary to start from the bottom.

MAIN PART

Local law enforcement officers and their duties and functions and cooperation. Neighborhood law enforcement agency (hereinafter referred to as "Maskan") is a neighborhood agency of internal affairs bodies, other law enforcement agencies, and public structures that directly implement the activities of maintaining public order in neighborhoods and villages, preventing offenses and fighting crime, as well as ensuring the safety and peace of citizens. It is the lowest level structural structure of the internal affairs bodies that organizes their joint work.

Requirements for shelter buildings and the procedure for carrying out activities in them are determined by the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Maskans perform their activities: senior inspector of prevention, inspector of prevention, assistant of public order of the inspector of prevention (on a daily basis); inspector of the district (city) internal affairs body assigned to serve in the region on women's issues, inspector of the probation department, operative representative, employees of the patrol post service; it is carried out by the National Guard unit, employees of other competent state bodies and representatives of public structures, sent to maintain public order and prevent crimes in the area. Organization of the activities of the Maskan The Senior Inspector of Prevention is the immediate head of the Maskan and is responsible for maintaining public order in the neighborhood (village) and effectively organizing daily work on crime prevention.

Head of residence:

Is personally responsible for the proper fulfillment of the tasks assigned to the residential activity;

supervises the performance of the tasks assigned to the employees operating in the area, determines the patrol routes in the area and organizes the patrol service;

coordinates the activities of the National Guard unit, employees of other authorized state bodies and representatives of public organizations sent to help maintain public order and crime prevention in the region;

approves the work plans of the settlement; submits a recommendation proposal to the public order assistant of the prevention inspector, who is diligently performing his duties, to be accepted for service in the internal affairs bodies in the prescribed manner;

Makes a direct proposal to the head of the regional internal affairs body to motivate the employees who perform effective work in Maskan; Performs other tasks within the competence of Maskan. In the absence of the senior inspector of prevention, his powers are exercised by the inspector of prevention.

Ensuring legality, the stability of the criminogenic situation in the neighborhood (rural) and the formation of a positive opinion in the public about the activities of law enforcement agencies are the main criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of the activities of Maskan.

The following are the main tasks of Maskan:

maintaining public order in the neighborhood (village), prevention of crimes, and direct implementation of the fight against crime;

to organize the cooperation of internal affairs bodies, other state bodies and public structures in the area of neighborhoods to ensure the safety and peace of citizens ;

solving the problems of the population, as well as organizing the social adjustment of persons who have suffered from crime, have antisocial behavior, and committed crimes;

Early prevention, detection and detection of offenses by means of unified centralized electronic surveillance and monitoring using video surveillance devices installed at the entrances and exits of the neighborhood (village) and other objects in the area.

CONCLUSION

On March 26, 2021, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to raise the activity of internal affairs bodies to a new level in terms of quality in the field of ensuring public safety and fighting crime" was adopted. In this Decree, it was

established that neighborhood law enforcement centers will be established on the basis of the bases of the internal affairs bodies. It should be noted that the neighborhood law enforcement agency is the main subordinate of ensuring public safety in the area, preventing offenses and fighting crime.

On the basis of Maskan, the relevant sectoral services of the local internal affairs bodies and the coordinated activities of the National Guard and other state bodies are organized. Also, the prevention inspector was entrusted with the task of systematic organization and coordination of work to ensure public safety, prevention of violations and fight against crime.

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